

Influence of Ecological factor on Mango Fruit Fly, *Bactrocera dorsalis* Hendel

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Abstract

The studies on seasonal incidence of mango fruit-fly indicated that pest was appeared in April to June. The influence of ecological factors, viz., biotic (host plant) and abiotic factors (weather parameters) on the abundance and population of fruit fly. *Bactrocera dorsalis* on mango were worked out. Peak incidence of fruit fly activity was observed during last week of May (6 to 9 infected fruits / 20 fruits). However, a gradual increase was observed during first week of April (24 infested fruits / 20 fruits) and declined during fourth week of June (5.7 infected fruits / 20 fruits). Correlation studies between incidence and weather parameters showed significant positive relationship with maximum and minimum temperatures and negatively correlated with rainfall and relative humidity (morning and evening). Older mango trees (15 and above years old) were more susceptible to fruit fly damage than young trees.

Key words : Abiotic factors. *Bactrocera dorsalis*, *Mangifera indica*, Varietal susceptibility

Introduction :

Mango, *Mangifera indica*, L., is the important fruit crop of the world, which is severely damaged by fruit fly. Nearly 250 insect and mite pest attack the tree in different stages. (Fasih and Srivastava, 1990). The most common species attacking mango crop is *Bactrocera dorsalis* Hendel. Varying incidence of fruit fly was seen in the mango orchards of, Tirupati on different varieties. The pest status does not remain static throughout the year but changes accordingly based on abiotic factors. The relative abundance of fruit fly incidence was also varied with varieties and age of the mango tree. The present investigation was aimed to study the ecological factors on the population fluctuation of fruit flies infesting mango (Srivastava, 1997).

Materials and Methods :

Studies on seasonal incidence and population fluctuation of fruit fly were carried out in mango orchard of C.S.A. Univ. of Agric. & Tech., Kanpur. The crop was observed at weekly intervals throughout the year for the incidence of mango fruit fly. Observations were recorded during morning to take the advantage of sedentary nature of insects. Seven trees were selected and from each tree, corresponding to four directions, four branches were jagged, and five fruits were observed for recording data. The total numbers of damaged

fruits were recorded by counting the number of damaged fruits in each tree.

Eight mango varieties viz., Neelum, Dashehari, Noor Jahan, Safeda, Alfanso, Sindoor, Chaunsa and Pairi were observed continuously to quantify the relative susceptibility of different mango varieties to fruit fly. From each variety, three trees of 15-20 years of age were selected for this study. Each tree was observed by fixing 4 sampled spots i.e. five fruits in each direction. The total numbers of damaged fruits were recorded by counting the number of damaged fruits in each tree. The data were subjected to statistical analysis after transformation.

Affect of abiotic factors on population dynamics of fruit fly in mango were carried out by correlating meteorological observations and fruit fly incidence. Data on all mean values for temperature (both maximum and minimum), (morning and evening, %) and total (mm) in different standard weeks were recorded from the meteorological observatory of C.S.A. Univ. of Agric. & Tech., Kanpur. Studies on the influence of age of the tree on the population dynamics of fruit fly was done on Neelum variety. Three distinct groups of trees viz., 0-5, 6-14 and >15 years old were selected for the study. Under each age group seven trees were selected for constant observation at weekly intervals. From each selected tree, twenty fruits were observed and data were subjected to statistical analysis.

Results and Discussion :

Moth of the adult mango fruit fly, *Bactrocera dorsalis* was dark brown colour with yellowish stripes on the abdomen. Females were generally bigger than males. The eggs were smooth, shiny white, translucent and banana shaped with one end pointed and the other blunt. The female inserts eggs deep into the fruit rind. The larvae (maggots) were dull white in colour with cylindrical body and always apodous. The pupa was a coarctate type with straw yellow coloured which later changes to dark brown. The newly hatched maggots penetrated into the fruit pulp to eat on it by forming tunnels in it. Fruit infestations result in their drop or make them unfit for consumption and rotten fruit skin giving odd sine II.

The occurrence of fruit fly coincided with semi-ripening and ripening stages of mango fruit. Both adults and maggots caused damage by ovipositional injury, feeding and rotting of fruits by maggots. The peak fruit fly population in mango was observed during fourth week of May (6-9 infected fruits/20 fruits). A gradual increase in population was observed from first week of April (2.6 in infected fruits/20 fruits) and subsequently, declined during last week of June (5.7 infected fruits/20 fruits). Correlation studies between incidence of fruit fly and weather parameters (Table 2) showed positive correlation with minimum ($r=0.7288$) and maximum temperatures ($r=0.8802$) and negatively correlated with rainfall ($r=0.0996$) and morning ($r=0.6772$) and evening ($r=0.5090$), the finding was in agreement with the reports of Reddy and Kumar (2005); Raj *et al.* (2000). The results on the interaction of temperatures with population fluctuation of use etc. pests were conformity with those of Rani *et al.*

(2004); Gulati (2004), who reported that positive correlation with maximum and minimum temperatures; negative correlation with rainfall.

Table 1 : Incidence of Fruit fly, *Bactrocera dorsalis* on mango.

Standard weeks	Number of damaged fruit/20 fruits	Standard weeks	Number of damaged fruits/20 fruits
9 March	0	17 May	5.5
10 March	0	18 May	6.2
11 March	0	19 May	6.6
12 March	0	20 May	6.4
13 April	2.6	21 June	6.4
14 April	3.0	22 June	5.5
15 April	3.7	23 June	5.0
16 April	4.4	24 June	5.7

Fig. No. 1 : Incidence of Fruit fly, *Bactrocera dorsalis* on mango.

All the varieties were found with mango fruit fly (Fig. 1), the infestation ranged with from 2.87 to 7.23 infestation fruits/20 fruits. Variety Cherakurasam showed less infestation (2.87 damaged fruits/20 fruits) while Swarnajahangir showed severe infestation (7.23 damaged fruits/20fruits), the other varieties viz., Rumani, Neeleshan, Bangalora, Neelum, Baneshan and Mulgoa had moderated infestation 93.23, 3.50, 4.93, 4.67, 5.83 and 6.33 damaged fruits/20 fruits). This variation is due to alteration of climatic factors. The results of the present study reports that the older mango trees (15 above years old) were

more susceptible to fruit fly damage (4.53 damaged fruits/20 fruits)(Fig. 1). Similarly, young mango trees (0-5 years old) were less susceptible to fruit fly (3.50 damaged fruits/20 fruits). Host preference was also studied by Rajpoot *et al.* (2002) and reported that among cucurbits, maximum emergence of fruit fly was found in watermelon followed by bottle gourd. The attack of fruit fly depended on the softness, tenderness and size of fruit which attributed to egg laying capacity of fruit fly, it was noticed that it laid more than one time.

Table 2: Relationship between weather parameter and fruit fly incidence

Correlation co-efficient	Temperature		Relative humidity		Rainfall
	Minimum	Maximum	Morning	Evening	
r	0.7288**	0.8802**	-0.6772**	-0.5090**	-0.0996 ^{NS}

Critical value rate (P = 0.05) = 0.2936
(P = 0.01) = 0.6542

** = Significant at (P = 0.01)
NS = Non significant

This clearly indicated that pest activity was greater during the month of May. It is a key time to impose chemical management practices, particularly in Southern parts of orchards. Fruit fly was regular and serious in nature. However, in this study, the variety like Noor Jahan was found comparatively with lower level of infestation. It was inferred that popularisation of these mango varieties and their derivatives in hot spots of fruit fly might be viable alternative at this juncture. This study also suggested that the aged trees should be protected during peak incidence of fruit fly to avoid quantitative and qualitative losses.

References :

- Chaudhary, S.K. (2015). Diversity and nature of damage of mango insect pests at Kalia Chak-II Block of Malda, W.B. (India). *J. Ent. & Zoo. Studies*, **3** (4) : 307-311.
- Fasih, M. and K. Srivastava (1990). Parasite and predators of insect pest of mango. *Insect Pest Control*, **32** (2) : 39-41.
- Gulati, Rachna (2004). Incidence of *Tetranychus cinnabarinus* infestation in different varieties of *Abelmoschus esculentus*. *Ann. Pl. Protec. Sci.* **12** : 45-47.
- More, S.A.; Shinde, B.D. and Kharat, R. (2011). Survey and seasonal abundance of chrysopids in mango ecosystem of Konkan region. *International J. Pl. Protection*, **4** (1) : 312-314.
- Rai, A.K., R.B.P. Sinha and A.K. Singh (2000). Effect of abiotic factors on the population of rice leaf folder. *Ann. Pl. Protec. Sci.*, **8**: 154-158.
- Rajpoot, S.K.S., S.Ali and SMA Rizvi (2002). Relative population and host preference of fruit fly. *Bactrocera dorsalis* on cucurbits. *Ann. Pt. Protec. Sci.*, **10**: 62-64.
- Rani, Seema, B.B. Goel and G.P. Gupta (2004). Effect of temperature on development and reproduction of *Spodoptera litura*. *Ann. Pt. Protec. Sci.*, **12** : 205-206.

- Reddy, N.A and C.T. Ashok Kumar (2005). Influence of weather factors on abundance and management of surpentine leaf miner on tomato. *Ann. Pt. Protec.Sci.*,**13**:315-318.
- Srivastava, R.P. (1997). Mango insect pest management. International Book Distributing Company, Lucknow, pp. 199.